

become too tall and prone to lodging. This type is best suited to conditions where the water depth is great and the water rise rate is rapid. However, even under deepwater conditions, the plant parts above the water level are too long

and the plants tend to lodge.

Type B is probably the optimum response for deep water. Even at medium-deepwater level, plants with type B reaction perform better because they are shorter than plants with type A.

Type C or intermediate height varieties with very limited elongation ability are possible for medium-deep water. Such plants, however, will not give reasonable yields in deeper water, even with the addition of N. ■

GENETIC EVALUATION AND UTILIZATION

Temperature tolerance

Cold-tolerant varieties from China

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Eleven best varieties based on cold tolerance at 4 growth stages have been selected from 1,474 Chinese varieties in the IRRI germplasm bank. The methods used for testing at the different growth stages were described in earlier papers. Early seedling stage was tested at 5°C, seedling stage at 12°C, panicle development stage and flowering stage at 15°C.

All entries (see table) are sinica except Hung Chao Lu Yu and Ai Yeh Lu. Ai Yeh Lu has short growth duration and Hung Chao Lu Yu has high protein content (13.1 to 13.6%). The agronomic characteristics of sinica varieties selected

Varieties cold tolerant at 4 stages.

Acc. no.	Variety	Cold tolerance score ^a			
		ES	SS	PD	FS
01178	Chiang Tsenf Tao Ju	1	3	2	1
01179	Hung Chao Lu Yu	1	3	3	2
01254	Y Chang Ju	1	3	3	3
01269	Ta Chang Kong	3	2	2	3
01385	Fang Chi	3	3	2	3
01395	Chu Cheng	3	3	3	3
07288	Fi-Lai-Feng	1	2	3	3
10360	Ai-Yeh Lu (PI 160965)	3	3	2	2
28474	Hsiung-Yo 613	3	2	2	3
36852	Ching-Hsi 15	1	3	2	3
36853	Ching-Hsi 17	1	2	2	3

^a ES = early seedling stage, SS = seedling stage, PD = panicle development, FS = flowering stage. 1 = good, 9 = poor.

do not differ greatly. Fi-Lai-Feng has a long maturity period, but is resistant to bacterial blight. Chu Cheng has the highest 1,000-grain weight.

Most of these donor varieties do not have disease and insect resistance.

Crosses with varieties resistant to diseases and insect pests and with good plant type are necessary to improve grain yield and general adaptability. Seeds for national breeding programs are available at IRRI. ■

Evaluation of rooting ability of rice in puddled soil in low temperature

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In areas where temperature is low during transplanting, recovery of rice varieties after transplanting is poor because of poor rooting ability. To develop a practical and efficient method of screening varieties for good rooting ability, entries in the 1980 International Rice Cold Tolerance Nursery were evaluated 23 days after transplanting at Banaue, Philippines, and 13 days after transplanting at Chuncheon, Korea. There were 245 entries at Banaue and 215 at Chuncheon. High-tillering and vigorous varieties were given a visual

Correlation coefficients among plant characters at Banaue, Philippines, and Chuncheon, Korea.

phenotypic score of 1; short and low-tillering varieties were scored 7.

At Banaue, 2 plants/entry were sampled to measure the characters under study; 1 plant/entry was sampled at Chuncheon. Correlation between and among the characters measured is shown in the figure. Root dry weight was considered an indicator of good rooting ability in low-temperature conditions.

Scores on phenotypic vigor of plants — scored on a 1-9 scale — were negatively correlated with other characters. A significant correlation between root dry weight and tiller number indicated

possible selection of plants that have good rooting ability on the basis of tiller number in low temperatures. This would eliminate the tedious work of carefully pulling the seedlings and washing the soil off the roots. Root length contributed much toward root dry weight, and a positive significant correlation between seedling height and root length revealed an indirect effect of seedling height on root dry weight. Tiller number, however, had no effect on root length at Banaue. In Chuncheon, Korea, phenotypic vigor was significantly correlated with root length and root dry weight, but not with tiller

number. Tiller number was significantly correlated with root dry weight, as in Banaue. But unlike in Banaue, the seedling height was significantly correlated with root dry weight — perhaps because the Banaue observation was taken at a later growth stage.

Results in Banaue and Chuncheon indicate that selection for plants with good tillering ability in low-temperature conditions will also select plants with good rooting ability. The early establishment of transplanted seedlings is important in low-temperature areas, which generally have short growing seasons. ■

Use of small pots for testing cold tolerance of crosses at seedling and flowering stages under rapid generation advance

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The rapid generation advance (RGA) program at IRRI generally uses small plastic square pots (5.5 × 5.5 × 5.0 cm). The practicality of these pots for screening or breeding during RGA was tested. Selection for low temperature tolerance was done at two plant stages: seedling and flowering. Selection at those stages is important in screening donor parents for cold tolerance crossing. The table shows the performance of seven cold tolerance crosses in small pots.

The F₂ seedlings were screened in a cold water tank at 12° C. Thirty percent of the seedlings were found tolerant of low temperature. The susceptible plants were discarded and the tolerant plants were grown under normal water temperatures.

During the flowering stage, the plants were placed in a dark room at 15° C for 3 days, and then taken back to the greenhouse (maximum temperature less than 30° C). The percentage of sterility was taken at harvest time and used as a criterion for selection. Plants with less than 30% sterility were selected.

The use of small square pots for cold tolerance screening at flowering was compared with that of the standard 4-liter pots. A set of 28 varieties were

Selection efficiency for 7 cold-tolerant crosses grown in small pots during the F₂. IRRI, 1980.

Cross	F ₂ seeds (no.) (A)	No. selected after screening			Selection efficiency (%)		
		At seedling stage (B)	At flowering stage (C)	B/A	C/A	C/B	
							Selection efficiency (%)
Silewah/IR3880-13	872	180	27	21	3	15	
IR3841-14-2-2-3/IET2815	849	235	73	28	9	31	
IET2815/IR6172-6-3	123	41	18	33	2	5	
iET2845/CRP6-1899-25/Cul. 854	444	145	53	33	12	37	
Taipei NO 309, B922c-Mr-91	114	60	14	53	12	23	
Taipei NO 309/IR26	500	272	21	54	4	8	
Dumsiah 81/RNR 7303	113	111	0	98	0	0	

planted in both pots. The results showed a highly significant correlation ($t = .7095^{**}$) indicating that the small pots can be used in screening for cold tolerance at flowering.

The study shows that during screening of low-temperature crosses, small pots are best used at the seedling and flowering stages. Their use will reduce the growth duration by 10 to 20 days (to an av of 90 days), plant height by 10 to 20 cm (to an av of 75 cm), and spikelet number by 20 spikelets/plant (to an av of 50). The reduction in spikelet number will not affect the breeding process, and

the shorter growth duration will hasten the breeding program. Use of small pots will involve the following steps:

1. Mix fine soil and fertilizer uniformly.
2. Use pregerminated seeds at 2 seeds/pot and thin out weak seedlings.
3. Place pots on pallets with plastic lining.
4. Supply adequate water to prevent the plants from drying.
5. There should be at least 2,000 plants for F₂ crosses. ■

Pest management and control

DISEASES

Preliminary studies on isolation and means of spread of the rice leaf scald fungus in Sierra Leone

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The incidence of leaf scald disease of rice caused by the fungus *Rhynchosporium oryzae* has increased in the past 4 years in Sierra Leone. Therefore, work was initiated to develop a technique to rapidly inoculate and screen for leaf